

Healthy Living Styles and Breast Cancer Awareness Preventive Measures Among Female Teachers of Special Needs Learners in Oyo

¹*Sanni Jamiu Abisoye, ¹Lala Abolaji Jolade & ¹Bernadette Sampson

*Corresponding author: sannij80@gmail.com

¹Federal College of Education (SP), Oyo

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11528156>

Abstract

This paper investigated healthy living styles and knowledge of breast cancer preventive measures among female teachers of special needs in Oyo. 50 participants mainly female teachers in Special schools were purposively selected to respond to a validated self designed questionnaire. The study descriptive survey research design. Three research questions were raised and answered. Data gathered were analyzed the descriptive statistics of simple percentage and frequency count. 90% of the participants know risk factors and causes of breast cancer while 96% maintain good health living, 96% shun smoking. The results favored healthy living styles and knowledge of breast cancer to prevent breast cancer among female teachers. Regular medical checkup, feeding on balance diet, and regular physical exercise were recommended to reduce the risks of breast cancer among female teacher or special needs teachers.

Keywords: Breast cancer, Healthy living Styles, Preventive measures, Special needs

Introduction

The present day society is filled with different health-disease challenges of different kinds, and cancer is one of the most serious and fearful disease threatening human life in this present day. Cancer is a medical general term for a large group of diseases that can affect any part of the body (WHO, 2013). Cancer is of different types such as lung, blood, prostate, kidney, liver, head and neck, cervical and breast cancer (WHO, 2013). Cancer is a medical term used to describe uncontrolled growth of abnormal cells anywhere in the body. Where this uncontrolled abnormal growth cell is found usually bears the adjective to qualify the cancer. Abnormal growth of uncontrolled cell found in the breast is referred to as breast cancer. Cancer of the breast domiciled in women and always dangerous and threaten to life and psycho wellbeing if not early detected and treatment is delayed (David, 1983 and Meena, 2013). According to Surjen (2013), breast cancer is a type of cancer that occur predominantly in women and its prevalence in men is rare. Breast cancer is the most dangerous and invasive form of cancer in female which requires aggressive prevention, treatment and management.

It is very widely in its clinical characteristics from stage zero to stage five.

- i. **Stage Zero:** The abnormal cells might have formed but not spread to the surrounding tissue with Zero pain or discomfort.
- ii. **Early Stage (Stage One):** The cancer may have spread to a small section of the surrounding tissue with less pain and discomfort.
- iii. **Localized Stage (Stage Two):** A tumor between 20 – 50mm in size will have been formed which may and may not involve the lymph nodes with significant medical implication.
- iv. **Regional spread (Stage Three):** The Tumor formed will be larger than 50mm in diameter involving the lymph nodes and spread toward the chest region. In some cases, the tumor of the body will no longer be present and metamorphous into full blown cancer with serious pain and unbearable discomfort.
- v. **Distanced Spread (Stage Four):** The cancer would have spread beyond the breast to other parts of the body with its clinical impact shown in the general health state of the patient (Surjen, 2013 & WHO, 2013).

Signs of breast cancer in women

Although breast cancer is threatening to the totality of human health, before its aggressive impact spread to almost all part of the body, It's usually gives symptoms at rare tender age. Its signs manifested through signs of carcinoma could embrace a lump within the breast, and amendment in breast form, dimpling of the skin and fluid coming back from the pap, a fresh inverted pap or a red scary patch of skin (Liolina, 2021). According to David (1983), the following are common signs of breast cancer in women:

- i. The woman may notice a lump, often in the part of the breast.
- ii. The breast may have an abnormal dent or dimple or many tiny pits like the skin of an orange.
- iii. Often there are large but painless lymph nodes in the armpit.
- iv. The lumps grow slowly. At first, it usually does not hurt or get hurt, later it may hot and hurt.

Self-examination of the women breast

It is medically advisable that every woman should learn how to examine her own breast for possible signs/symptoms of breast cancer. It is highly medical to do it once in a month, preferable on the 10th day after the menstrual period started. individual should look at the breast carefully if there is any noticeable different in size or shape of the two breasts. Also, there is need to squeeze the nipples and check whether blood or a discharge comes out. Lying with a pillow under her back and feel the breasts with the flats fingers, press the breasts and roll it beneath the finger tips, she should start near the nipple and go around the breast and move up into the armpit. If carefully done, any hidden lumps would be revealed.

Risk Factors and causes of Breast Cancer among Women

The development of breast cancer could be traced to: gender and age, genetic makeup, life style habits and diets, obesity, alcohol, heavy smoking, previous medical history, hormone replacement, exposure to radiation, reproductive history, unhealthy living style, hormonal factors and personal history of breast cancer (David, 1983), Liolina (2021), Meena (2013) and World health Organization (WHO, 2023).

Preventive Measures against Breast Cancer Among Women

Prevention is always better and cheaper than cure. Breast cancer is a preventive disease. The following preventive measures are suggested against breast cancer.

- i. Self breast examination: Clinical breast examination, healthy living styles, appropriate and regular exercise, balance diet, avoidance or reduced alcohol intake.
- ii. Avoidance of heavy smoking, medical checkup and stay update on information on causes of breast cancer as well as guide against risk factors of breast cancer.

Treatment of Breast Cancer

A correct breast cancer diagnosis is essential for appropriate and effective treatment because it is clinically established that every cancer type required a specific treatment regimen. Treatment for breast cancer usually includes three phase: Surgery, radiotherapy and or systematic therapy (chemotherapy). In Nigeria, the cost of

breast cancer treatment depends on various factors such as, the treatment option chosen, the stage of the cancer, location of the hospital, such hospital and duration of treatment. Sometimes age and status of the patient could also be a factor (Surjen, 2013).

Fact sheet and prevalence of breast cancer

Breast cancer is a type of cancer that begins in the cells of the breast. It can occur in both men and women but is more common in women. Mammogram, Biopsy and MRI or Ultra sound is a way of diagnosing breast cancer. Survival rate of breast cancer varies by stage and individual factors, early detection includes prognosis. Cancer is a leading cause of death worldwide. Accounting nearly 10 million deaths in 2020 or nearly one in six deaths. The most common cancers are breast, lung, colon and rectum and prostate cancers. About 1/3 of deaths from cancer are due to heavy smoking of tobacco, high consumption of alcohol, low fruit and vegetable intake, lack of physical activities and obesity.

According to WHO, 2017 Cancer is a dangerous and killer disease. Medical record shows that it is a leading cause of death worldwide. Accounting that nearly Ten (10) million deaths in 2020 in terms of new cases of cancer were:

- i. Breast: 2.26 million cases
- ii. Lung: 2.21 million cases
- iii. Colon and Rectum: 1.93 million cases
- iv. Prostrate: 1.41 million cases
- v. Stomach: 1.09 million cases
- vi. Skin (Non melanoma): 1.20 million cases

The most common causes of cancer death in 2020 were:

- i. Lung: 1.80 million cases
- ii. Colon and Rectum: 916, 000 death
- iii. Liver 83, 000 death
- iv. Stomach: 769, 000 death
- v. Breast: 685, 000 death

Each year, approximately 400,000 children develop cancer (WHO, 2023). According to America cancer society (2023), about 297, 790 new cases of invasive breast cancer will be diagnose in woman and about 48, 700 women will die from breast cancer. They also confirm that breast cancer merely occurs in middle age and older women. Thus, the female teachers of person with special needs need to aware of symptoms of breast cancer, causes of breast cancer, health and social implication as well as financial boding of treating and managing breast cancer.

Only the healthy teacher will cater for the needs of the educational needs of the children under him or her. Special educators play roles more than teacher to the special needs, thus there is need to give their health priority.

Statement of the Problem

Cancer has been found out medically to be a leading cause of death among men and women especially breast cancer that is commonly affect women with symptoms of profound bone pain, swollen humus nodes, shortness of breath, or yellow skin are common symptoms of breast cancer which normally impair total health of the patient and disassociate her for academic and social responsibilities. The teacher of the special needs learners with medical case of breast cancer will not be able to perform her psychological and academic responsibilities, if affected. Thus, there is need to prevent breast cancer with optimum preventive measures by knowing its symptoms, causal factors, risk factors, preventive measures as well as treatment and management available. This is where the topic comes in; healthy living styles and breast cancer awareness preventive measures among female teachers of special needs learners.

Purpose of the study

The general purpose of this research is to research examine the healthy living styles and breast cancer awareness preventive measures among female teachers of special needs learners in Oyo.

The specific purposes are:

- i. To determine whether the female teachers have knowledge about risk factors/causes of breast cancer.
- ii. To determine whether the female teachers have knowledge about symptoms of breast cancer
- iii. To determine healthy living styles among female teachers

Research questions

- i. What are the risk factors/causes of breast cancers among female teachers?
- ii. What are the symptoms of breast cancer among female teachers?
- iii. What are the healthy living style practices among the female teachers?

Research methodology

The method adopted was a descriptive survey research. The research population of the study consisted of fifty (50) female teachers with no medical record of breast cancer from Durbar School of handicap Oyo and Federal College of Education (Special) Oyo. The participants were purposively selected and used as sample for the study. Age of participants range between 30 – 55 years.

Instrumentation

The research use for this study was a self designed skill which is named Healthy living styles and breast cancer awareness preventive measures. Questionnaire which is coined “HELSCAPM”. This 20 Item questionnaire was self developed. This was essentially designed to probe into healthy living styles and knowledge of cancer, preventive measures among female teachers of special needs learners. Before the questionnaire was administered, it was validated and a reliability of 0.85 was obtained using Cronbach alpha gave. It was Likert scale questionnaires of options YES and NO.

Method of data analysis

The researcher administered the questionnaire to each participant one after the other. The questionnaire was administered under conducive atmosphere. The researcher ensure that the respondents filled the questionnaire properly. Data gathered was analyzed with the use of descriptive statistics frequency counts and percentages.

Result and discussion

The findings of this study in relation to the research questions are presented in table 1 – 3 and subsequently discussed.

Research Question 1: What are the risk factors/causes of breast cancers among female teachers?

Table 1:

S/N	Items	Frequency		Percentage	
		YES	NO	YES	NO
1.	Do you know that age is one of the risk factors of breast cancer?	50	00	100	00
2.	Do you know that breast cancer is gender related?	45	05	95	05
3.	Do you know that genetic factor can cause breast cancer?	40	10	90	10
4.	Do you know that hormonal factor cause breast cancer?	48	02	98	02
5.	Do you know that exposure to certain environmental factor can cause breast cancer?	50	00	100	00

The result from the table above shows that, most of the respondents know the risk factors of breast cancer. More than 90% aware the risk factors of breast cancer while less 10% do not know

Research Question 2: What are the symptoms of breast cancer among female teachers?

Table 2:

S/N	Items	Frequency		Percentage	
		YES	NO	YES	NO
6.	Do you know that lump in the breast or under arm is often noticeable symptoms of breast cancer?	50	00	100	00
7.	Do you know that changes in breast size is associated with breast cancer?	50	00	100	00
8.	Do you know that changes in nipple, position, inversion or discharge especially, if it is bloody is a symptoms of breast cancer?	50	00	100	00
9.	Do you know that changes in skin texture is a common symptom of breast cancer?	50	00	100	00
10.	Do you know that unexplained redness or warmth on the breast is related to breast cancer?	50	00	100	00

The result above reveals that participants know the symptoms of breast cancer. The 100% of the participants were aware of the symptoms of breast cancer among female teachers.

Research Question 3: What are the healthy living practices among the female teachers?

Table 3:

S/N	Items	Frequency		Percentage (%)	
		YES	NO	YES	NO
6.	Do you feed on balance diet?	50	00	100	00
7.	Do you smoke?	04	48	02	96
8.	Do you take alcohol?	10	40	20	80
9.	Do you regularly exercise your body?	35	15	70	30
10.	Do you take birth control?	40	10	80	20

The table above shows that healthy living practices among the participants above average 100% of the participants maintain good feeding habit 80% do not take alcohol, 96% do not smoke, 70% involved in body exercise, and 80% practices birth control.

Discussion of findings

In answering the question, which says, what are the risk factors or causes of breast cancer among female teachers. Table 1 shows that 90% picked yes that they have knowledge of risk factors/causes of breast cancer while 5% were not. This collaborate the study of David (1983), WHO (2013) and Liolina (2021). The result from table

shows that participants have the knowledge of symptoms of breast cancer among female teachers, knowing symptoms of an ailments is also parts of prevention and treatment as submitted by WHO (2013)

Almost all the participants have good health cultures which serve as boundary between them and breast cancer. As 100% feed on balance diet, 80% knows that breast cancer can lead to cancer, 70% do regularly exercise their body and 80% do not take alcohol. These causes of breast cancer are: gender and age, genetic makeup, life style habits and diets, obesity, alcohol, heavy smoking, previous medical history, hormone replacement, exposure to radiation, reproductive history, unhealthy living style, hormonal factors and personal history of breast cancer as submitted by WHO (2013), Meena (2013), American Cancer Society (2023).

Conclusion

Breast cancer is a deadly disease that can be prevented. Its preventive is cheaper and easier. Feeding on balance diet, avoidance of alcohol, abstinence from smoking, regular body exercise as well as regular medical check-up are established as best way to prevent breast cancer. Any symptoms of breast cancer noticed should be given aggressive medical intervention. It is medically established that breast cancer can be medically managed and treated, but its prevention is better than cure.

Recommendations

- i. Regular medical check – up should be encouraged among women.
- ii. Attending health seminar and workshop should be encouraged for female teachers
- iii. Female teachers should form tradition of reading health tips on breast cancer and other associated diseases.
- iv. Any symptoms of breast cancer and any other Deadly diseases should be reported to appropriate medical quarters.

Reference

- American Cancer Society (2023). *Key statistics for Breast Cancer*. Retrieved online. <https://www.Cancer.org.2023>.
- David, W. (1983). *Where there is no doctor*. A village health care handbook for Africa. Macmillan Publisher.
- Liolina, (2021). Sign and symptoms of breast cancer. *European Journal of clinical Oncology*,.3,(S2), 001. Retrieved online: <https://www.google.com>
- Meena, K. (2013). *What is cancer?* Lecture note. Retrieved online: <https://www.researchgate.net>.
- Surjen (2013). *Early Stage Breast Cancer*. First stage breast cancer. <https://www.surge.com/google>.

World Health Organization (2022). *Key facts on cancer*. <https://www.who.int>

World Health Organization (2023). *Fact sheets on Cancer*. <https://www.who.int.goggle>